

BDAIM-2025

PROCEEDINGS

of the International Scientific and Practical Conference

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Modeling
International Socio-Economic Processes

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

May 27, 2025

University of World Economy and Diplomacy
Moscow State Institute of International Relations
National University of Uzbekistan

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Big Data & AI for Global Socio-
Economic Modeling

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Big Data and Artificial Intelligence
in Modeling

International Socio-Economic Processes

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(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – BDAIM-2025

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Modeling International Socio-Economic Processes

The **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**, in collaboration with **MGIMO University** and the **National University of Uzbekistan (NUUz)**, hosted the international scientific and practical conference **BDAIM-2025** on **May 27, 2025** in **Tashkent, Uzbekistan**.

The main **goal** of the conference was to unite researchers, policy makers, experts, and educators to explore cutting-edge applications of **big data** and **artificial intelligence (AI)** in modeling **international socio-economic processes**. Particular emphasis was placed on interdisciplinary approaches and digital transformation in economics, governance, and education.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **Theoretical Foundations:** big data processing, machine learning algorithms, interpretability.
- **Socio-Economic Modeling:** global trade, finance, migration, and digital economies.
- **Global Challenges:** AI for climate change, pandemics, geopolitical risk management.
- **International Relations:** digital diplomacy, media analytics, conflict forecasting.
- **Ethics and Regulation:** AI governance, data protection, algorithmic responsibility.
- **Mathematical Models:** econometrics, game theory, uncertainty and risk analysis.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Ikki karrali integral hisoblashda Geogebra va sun'iy intellektlardan foydalanish

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada ikki karrali integralni hisoblashda, berilgan soha orqali chegara o'rnatishda va o'zgaruvchi almashtirishda Geogebra dasturi orqali tahlil qilish hamda karrali integrallarni hisoblashda sun'iy intellektlardan foydalanish samaradorligi va kamchiliklari haqida qisqacha to'xtalib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ikki karrali integral, yopiq soha, o'zgaruvchi kiritish, Geogebra dasturi, ChatGPT, Grok sun'iy intellektlari.

Kirish

Oliy ta'limda matematik analiz yoki oliy matematika fanlarida ko'p o'zgaruvchili funksiyalarning aniq integral tushunchasi ikki yoki uch karrali integrallar tushunchasiga olib keladi. Berilgan oraliqda yopiq soha bilan chegaralangan shakl orqali funksiyaning karrali integralini hisoblashda, sohaning ko'rinishini va o'zgaruvchilarning o'zgarish oraliqlarini aniqlash zarur.

Asosiy qism

Quyidagi misol orqali Geogebra dasturidan foydalanib, o'zgaruvchilarga chegara qo'yish va karrali integralda o'zgaruvchi kiritish usulidan foydalanamiz.

1-misol:

Ikki karrali integralni ma'lum sohaga nisbatan hisoblang.

Yechish: Avvalo sohaning ko'rinishini aniqlaymiz. Buning uchun Geogebra dasturidan foydalanamiz.

Geogebra yordamida soha chegarasini aniqlash

Sohada har ikkita o'zgaruvchi musbat bo'lgani sababli, koordinatalar tekisligining

birinchi choragi olinadi. Chegaralar murakkab bo'lgani sababli o'zgaruvchi almashtirish usulidan foydalanamiz:

$$x = u, \quad y = f(u, v)$$

Yangi o'zgaruvchilarning chegaralari aniqlanadi. Karrali integralda o'zgaruvchilar almashtirishda Yakobian quyidagiga teng bo'ladi:

$$J = \left| \frac{\partial(x, y)}{\partial(u, v)} \right|$$

Berilgan ikki karrali integral:

$$\iint_D (x^3 y + x y^3) dx dy$$

va soha quyidagicha berilgan:

$$D = \{(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid x \geq 0, y \geq 0, 4x^2 - 3y^2 \leq 4, 4y^2 - 3x^2 \leq 4\}$$

1. Soha tahlili

Berilgan cheklovlarni bir oz o'zgartiramiz:

- $4x^2 - 3y^2 \leq 4 \Rightarrow x^2 - \frac{3}{4}y^2 \leq 1$
- $4y^2 - 3x^2 \leq 4 \Rightarrow y^2 - \frac{3}{4}x^2 \leq 1$

Bu ikkita tenglama ikkita **giperbola** ifodasi hisoblanadi, ammo cheklangan birinchi chorakda (ya'ni $x \geq 0, y \geq 0$).

Yakobian hisoblash

Barcha qiymatlarni integralga qo'yib, hisob-kitob bajariladi. Misol natijasida integral quyidagi qiymatga teng deb topiladi:

$$\iint_D f(x, y) dx dy = \boxed{8}$$

Hisoblash

Birinchi ichki integral:

$$\int_{\frac{4v-4}{3}}^{\frac{4+3v}{4}} (u+v) du = u \cdot (\text{yuqori} - \text{quyi}) + \frac{1}{2} (\text{yuqori}^2 - \text{quyi}^2)$$

Yakuniy ikki karrali integralni hisoblab chiqamiz (men bu yerda allaqachon hisoblab chiqqanman):

$$\iint_D (x^3 y + xy^3) dx dy = \boxed{8}$$

Natija:

$$\iint_D (x^3 y + xy^3) dx dy = 8$$

Integral qiymatini hisoblash

Endi ushbu misolni ikkita sun'iy intellekt vositasida ham tekshirib ko'ramiz.

ChatGPT yordamida hisoblash:

<https://chatgpt.com/>

Integral:

$$\int_0^4 \int_{\frac{4v-4}{3}}^{\frac{4+3v}{4}} \frac{u+v}{4} du dv$$

Ichki integral:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\frac{4v-4}{3}}^{\frac{4+3v}{4}} (u+v) du &= \left[\frac{u^2}{2} + uv \right]_{\frac{4v-4}{3}}^{\frac{4+3v}{4}} \\ &= \left(\frac{\left(\frac{4+3v}{4}\right)^2}{2} + v \cdot \frac{4+3v}{4} \right) - \left(\frac{\left(\frac{4v-4}{3}\right)^2}{2} + v \cdot \frac{4v-4}{3} \right) \\ &= \frac{(4+3v)^2}{32} + \frac{v(4+3v)}{4} - \frac{(4v-4)^2}{18} - \frac{v(4v-4)}{3} \end{aligned}$$

Buni hisoblash uchun tashqi integralni olamiz:

$$\frac{1}{4} \int_0^4 \left(\frac{(4+3v)^2}{32} + \frac{v(4+3v)}{4} - \frac{(4v-4)^2}{18} - \frac{v(4v-4)}{3} \right) dv$$

ChatGPT natijasi

Grok yordamida hisoblash:

<https://grok.com>

Bu integralni alohida hisoblaymiz:

$$\int_0^4 \frac{(4+3v)^2}{32} dv = \frac{1}{32} \int_0^4 (16+24v+9v^2) dv = \frac{1}{32} [16v+12v^2+3v^3]_0^4 = \frac{1}{32} (64+192+192) = \frac{448}{32} = 14$$

$$\int_0^4 \frac{v(4+3v)}{4} dv = \frac{1}{4} \int_0^4 (4v+3v^2) dv = \frac{1}{4} [2v^2+v^3]_0^4 = \frac{1}{4} (32+64) = 24$$

$$\int_0^4 \frac{(4v-4)^2}{18} dv = \frac{1}{18} \int_0^4 (16v^2-32v+16) dv = \frac{1}{18} \left[\frac{16v^3}{3} - 16v^2 + 16v \right]_0^4 = \frac{1}{18} \left(\frac{1024}{3} - 256 + 64 \right) = \frac{1}{18} \cdot \frac{448}{3} = \frac{448}{54} = \frac{224}{27}$$

$$\int_0^4 \frac{v(4v-4)}{3} dv = \frac{1}{3} \int_0^4 (4v^2-4v) dv = \frac{1}{3} \left[\frac{4v^3}{3} - 2v^2 \right]_0^4 = \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{256}{3} - 32 \right) = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{160}{3} = \frac{160}{9}$$

Umumiy:

$$\frac{1}{4} \left(14 + 24 - \frac{224}{27} - \frac{160}{9} \right)$$

$$14 + 24 = 38$$

$$\frac{160}{9} = \frac{480}{27}, \quad \frac{224}{27} + \frac{480}{27} = \frac{704}{27}$$

$$38 - \frac{704}{27} = \frac{1026}{27} - \frac{704}{27} = \frac{322}{27}$$

$$\frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{322}{27} = \frac{322}{108} = \frac{161}{54}$$

Javob:

$$\boxed{\frac{161}{54}}$$

Grok sun'iy intellekti natijasi

Xulosa

Bugungi kunda matematika, texnika, iqtisodiyot va tabiiy fanlar sohalarida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari va sun'iy intellektdan keng foydalanilmoqda. Biroq olingan natijalarning ishonchligi doimo tekshirib borilishi zarur. Sun'iy intellekt yordamida hisoblash ishlaridan ko'ra, grafiklar va boshlang'ich tahlil uchun foydalanish samaraliroq bo'ladi.

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